

Iconic Tourist Attraction, Existential Authenticity, Place Attachment, and Emotional Solidarity of Tourists Visiting Tourism Villages: The Mediating Role of Cultural Heritage Tourism on Destination Loyalty

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Abstract

Local traditions are well-received by tourists. Some tourist communities may evolve into destinations. In Toba Samosir Regency tourist communities, cultural heritage tourism-mediated destination loyalty is influenced by iconic tourist attractions, existential authenticity, place connection, and emotional solidarity. In this investigation, descriptive quantitative methodologies are implemented. Non-probability and selective sampling were employed to sample repeat tourist town visitors in this study. A total of 155 individuals participated in the online survey. Utilized PLS-SEM to evaluate hypotheses. Heritage tourism partially enhances destination loyalty, while iconic tourist attraction, existential authenticity, and place attachment only slightly increase heritage tourism. The emotional solidarity of visitors is considerably enhanced by the connection to the place of Visitor Attractions, while existential authenticity is positively impacted, albeit not significantly. Emotional solidarity and historical tourism serve as mediators that enhance destination loyalty. Other studies, such as this one on the appeal of travelers to tourist communities, concentrate on environmental issues, investment, and tourism infrastructure. This study emphasizes the role of historical tourism, place attachment, affective solidarity toward destination loyalty, existential authenticity, and iconic tourist appeal as mediating variables. The research's recommendations have the potential to assist local governments and tourism sector participants in the development and expansion of visitor communities.

Keyword: Tourism; Destination; village; culture

1. INTRODUCTION

The 2023 Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy study shows that tourist communities have grown significantly. Tourist communities have become popular since the COVID-19 outbreak, with visitation rising 30–50% in two years, particularly in Central, East, and West Java. According to this report, Indonesia has 1,836 tourist villages on eight islands: Sumatra, Java, Kalimantan, Sulawesi, Nusa Tenggara, Maluku, and Papua. Pioneering, developing, advanced, and independent tourist communities are on the eight islands. Seventy percent of tourist communities will be pioneering and growing in 2021, while 30 percent will be advanced and autonomous. By 2024, the government wants 244 tourism settlements to be sophisticated and independent ([Kemenparekraf, 2021](#)).

Cultural heritage tourism as a promotional technique has increased in recent years. Tourists can benefit from existential experiences in cultural heritage sites by achieving fulfillment, mastery, or happiness ([Kolar & Zabkar, 2010](#)). Long-term, these happy dispositions should lead to faithful actions like coming back for more. Previous studies have

mainly concentrated on objective authenticity and integrity ([Sufyati et al., 2023](#)). However, there are a few notable outliers (which themselves yield mixed data).

Existential authenticity has been shown to powerfully and positively affect cultural heritage tourism loyalty ([Bryce et al., 2015](#)) or no commitment ([Q. B. Zhou et al., 2013](#)), depending on the source. Also, when thinking about loyal people, we have not taken into account the underlying qualities of authenticity ([Yi et al., 2017](#)), who evaluated loyalty from multiple perspectives ([Kolar & Zabkar, 2010](#)) and primarily focused on the individual level of existential authenticity ([Fu, 2020](#)).

Cognitive appraisal theory states customers' responses occur in a 'behavioral-emotional-cognitive' order ([Breitsohl & Garrod, 2016](#)). The existential impact of authenticity on the sub-dimensions of loyalty has yet to be individually identified despite earlier studies suggesting cognitive, affective, and behavioral elements of loyalty in various circumstances ([Meng & Han, 2019](#)). Nonetheless, it is plausible that multiple existential components of authenticity have varying impacts on visitor loyalty. This is a largely uncharted territory.

However, viewing the traveler's experience from an existential authenticity perspective is crucial ([Kapitan et al., 2022](#)). This study avoids the generalization of existential authenticity by adopting a framework that allows for critical discourse, creating an environment where individuals can use their travels to seek meaning and grow. Some forms of tourism, such as those classified as "heritage" ([Gavrili- Alexandris, 2015](#); [Shepherd, 2015](#)), "volunteer tourism" ([Kontogeorgopoulos, 2017](#)), or "pilgrimage" ([Árvavölgyi & Sági, 2019](#); [Damari & Mansfeld, 2016](#); [Kontogeorgopoulos, 2017](#)), provide a sense of freedom that allows for more profound personal encounters. Other visitor sectors - e.g., those simply searching for show, imagination, and fun - are irrelevant to that goal of authenticity. Empirical research reveals that levels of existential authenticity vary across the spectrum of tourism experiences. The effect was much more significant in the cultural heritage/sightseeing/amusement park tourism village and backpacking/volunteer categories than in the beach holidays for the sunbathing type ([Kirillova et al., 2017](#)). Even though many studies have found connections between attachment ([Hsu & Scott, 2020](#); [Kirillova et al., 2017](#); [J. Lee et al., 2012](#); [Prayag & Lee, 2019](#); [Prayag & Ryan, 2012](#)) and loyalty ([Patwardhan et al., 2020](#)), it is unclear which factor is more critical in fostering loyalty. Affective constructs are taken into account in other works as a means of explaining people's loyalty. This effort aims to advance an integrative moderated mediation model that shows how the two iconic constructs of tourist attraction, existential authenticity, place attachment, and emotional solidarity, have the potential to explain individual loyalty to tourist villages and how cultural heritage tourism can moderate this relationship ([Joo et al., 2020](#)).

When it comes down to it, a community's level of loyalty is a good measure of whether or not cultural heritage tourism in a tourist village will be successful at drawing in visitors and keeping them there in the long run by providing a sense of iconic attractiveness, existential authenticity, place attachment, and emotional solidarity ([Tsaour et al., 2019](#)). Planners will be better able to assess the performance of a tourism village and the future viability of cultural heritage tourism to promote destination loyalty and tourist visits if they have a better understanding of individual intentions in retrospect ([Sufyati et al., 2023](#)).

Very few scholars have studied the idea of destination loyalty as it relates to cultural heritage tourism ([Fu, 2020](#); [Hall et al., 2016](#); [Yi et al., 2018](#)). However, this study's primary objective is to examine the impact of existential authenticity on tourists' loyalty to destinations that feature cultural heritage by incorporating the novel variables of place attachment, iconic

tourist attraction, and emotional solidarity. This lesson aims to evaluate the contribution of cultural heritage tourism's mediation of iconic tourist attractions, existential authenticity, place attachment, and emotional solidarity to visitor loyalty, focusing on the latter two concepts. Visitor visits to communities in Toba Samosir Regency are expected to rise thanks to mediation by cultural heritage tourism.

Their research provides a thorough framework for describing the bonds between visitors and famous landmarks. If tourist villages want to attract more visitors, they must figure out how to include Existential Authenticity into destination loyalty. As a result, cultural heritage tourism can mediate between a strong sense of connection to a site and the economic benefits of increased tourism ([Ashworth, 2000](#); [Atzeni et al., 2022](#); [Nixon, 2022](#); [Poria et al., 2001](#)). The two additional variables, iconic tourist attraction and place attachment, were added to the ones used in previous research by Stern to better understand the potential of cultural heritage tourism as an access method for destination loyalty to increase tourist visits to tourist villages ([Stern et al., 2022](#)).

There is a pressing need to investigate methods that stakeholders in the tourism sector can employ to encourage more people to visit the tourist villages in Samosir Regency through the medium of cultural heritage tourism by incorporating iconic tourist attractions, existential authenticity, place attachment, and emotional solidarity. To make the best judgments, tourist industry operators must have an empirically proven model that contains notions connected to capacities in destination loyalty mediated by cultural heritage tourism. To address these issues and contribute substantially to the existing literature, especially in the context of worldviews, the studies reported in this journal investigate the impact of existential authenticity, place attachment, and iconic tourist attraction on destination loyalty in cultural heritage tourism. They are centered around visiting historical sites.

This study will formulate questions about the impact of cultural heritage tourism's ability to mediate the connection between iconic tourist attractions, the existential authenticity of place attachment, emotional solidarity, and destination loyalty. This research also seeks answers to whether the genuineness of renowned tourist sites, Existential Authenticity, place attachment, and emotional solidarity might, directly and indirectly, predict destination loyalty. A thorough literature review is offered first, followed by formulating hypotheses. Following this, the research technique is outlined, and finally, the outcomes, findings, and inferences are discussed.

The perpetuation of stories surrounding the creation of specific fashion icons is attributable to authenticity conveyed through legacy and ties to historical events ([Molleda, 2010](#)). Authenticity can be applied to objects: iconic and indexical ([Grayson & Martinec, 2004](#)). Authenticity can be both a social construction and a piece of proof. The term "index" is used to describe a gesture that has both a factual and a spatiotemporal relationship with something else, such as the relationship between an actor and his fingerprint ([Arroyo et al., 2023](#); [Florido-Benítez, 2023](#); [Kong et al., 2022](#); [Paras et al., 2022](#)). To use something as an indicator, one must accept the existence of the connection; this acceptance can come from the consumer's experience. A physical manifestation of an object is considered "authentic" if it is similar to an indexically authentic example ([Yi et al., 2018](#)). A person's preexisting knowledge or expectations are necessary to recognize an icon comparable to anything else.

The term "iconicity" refers to the process of comparing the actual manifestation of something to the indexically authentic version in one's head using a mental template (such as iconicity with history, fiction, or old items) or "composite images" ([Penton-Voak et al., 2006](#);

[Q. B. Zhou et al., 2013](#)). It influences social and cultural aspirations and product marketability while sparking conversations about the past, the present, and the future. Iconic tourist destinations have been shown to affect cultural history ([Ramírez & Portillo, 2020](#)). Nonetheless, my findings suggest legacy tourism mediates tourist destinations' iconicity and visitor loyalty. Physical characteristics (indexically) and the spirit of a brand (iconically) both serve as symbols of authenticity. Consumers can evaluate the authenticity of iconic attractions in a continuous spectrum from very iconic to merely indexical ([Hall et al., 2016](#)). However, a visitor's interest cannot be defined as an icon without possessing indexical significance. The type of primary tourist draw includes more authentic destinations in terms of their indexical and iconic value. This leads us to the study's first hypothesis: H1: Iconicity of Visitor Attractions Has a Positive Influence on Heritage Tourism.

Research on authenticity in the tourism industry focuses on travelers' evaluations of the genuineness of their experiences. Existential authenticity is a cornerstone of both subjectivity and objectivity since it prioritizes things like contentment, self-actualization, self-discovery, being yourself, and a sense of belonging to the world, other people, and one's history and culture ([Jyotsna & Maurya, 2019](#); [M. Kim & Kim, 2020](#); [Q. B. Zhou et al., 2013](#)). Tourists can gain a more reflective understanding of themselves and a more balanced outlook on life as a result of their travels ([Jyotsna & Maurya, 2019](#); [Ng et al., 2022](#); [Yi et al., 2017](#)), and others have all done excellent work expanding our understanding of existential authenticity through either conceptual or qualitative analysis.

A commonly accepted argument is that tourists travel to escape their everyday lives ([Brown, 2013](#)). Recent studies have contested reductionist, context-free definitions of authenticity in travel ([Brown, 2013](#); [Manthiou et al., 2018](#); [Södergren, 2021](#)). Authenticity is not exclusive to tourists, and not all forms of tourism allow a person to meet their actual self. While some vacationers go for nothing more than enjoyment and family time, others go in search of further ([Shang et al., 2020](#); [G. Wang et al., 2022](#)); rather than focusing solely on the tourism experience, several researchers have argued that it is more important to address the existential concerns of visitors, such as the authenticity of life. The extent to which visitors can achieve existential authenticity depends on how well they prepare for and engage with their travels. Even though trips can spark moments of existential authenticity, it has been stated that the United States "has not yet uncovered the truly transformative nature of tourist experiences" and that "a differentiated approach to tourism" is needed.

Needed: an appreciation for existential dread ([Arumugam et al., 2023](#)). Most empirical studies view authenticity in tourist attractions as a precursor to existential authenticity ([Arumugam et al., 2023](#); [Fu, 2020](#); [Yi et al., 2018](#); [Q. B. Zhou et al., 2013](#)). It has been argued recently that existential authenticity does not need a particular purpose ([Q. B. Zhou et al., 2013](#)). The tourist's or subject's own internal worldview, rather than any objective truth, is where existential authenticity is found ([Arumugam et al., 2023](#); [Fu, 2020](#); [G. Wang et al., 2022](#); [Yi et al., 2017, 2018](#); [Yuksel et al., 2010](#)). This may have nothing to do with the genuineness of the tourist attraction but instead with the activity or interest itself driving the truthfulness of the perspective. To sum up, the integrity of a tourist attraction has nothing to do with the validity of one's existential experience. A closer analysis of existential authenticity finds two components in the available literature: intrapersonal (connection with oneself) and interpersonal (relationship with others). This leads us to the study's second hypothesis: H2: Iconicity of Visitor Attractions positively influences Heritage Tourism.

This theoretical framework accounts for the correlation between visitors' emotional

investment in landmarks of cultural heritage and their belief in those landmarks' genuineness. Place attachment is considered a cause of authenticity perception ([Gillespie et al., 2022](#); [Qing et al., 2022](#)), and heritage tourism moderates this relationship. As a result, "tourist attractions and the social construction around them cannot be separated from the experience itself when analyzing it" ([Blešić et al., 2022](#)). The perceived authenticity of a tourist attraction can be affected by factors such as the significance of the location's history and the iconic status of the interest itself.

This is especially pertinent to cultural heritage tourism sites since people go there "to experience authentic places, artifacts, and activities representing stories and people from the past and the present." this describes how the unique characteristics of Appalachian cuisine in rural Asheville are reflected in the sincerity of the town's Farmers Market and local festivities. This is similar to how the "real" Eiffel Tower in Paris is (necessarily) an essential part of the place branding strategy of Paris and France ([Bernardo, 2013](#)). The Guggenheim-Bilbao Museum effect is an example of the embeddedness of an iconic building within its territory ([Bonnes et al., 2017](#); [Hidalgo & Hernández, 2001](#); [Suntikul & Jachna, 2016](#)). Therefore, it is anticipated that the visitor attraction's iconicity and the destination region's cultural and historical value may determine the influence of personal inclination towards place attachment on perceived authenticity. The third hypothesis is based on this moderation model and states: H3: Place Attachment Has a Positive Influence on Heritage Tourism.

To date, tourism studies on emotional solidarity have focused solely on residents' interests and construction perspectives with visitors ([Patwardhan et al., 2020](#)) or visitors' views of the building's effect on locals. Subsequently, the emotional solidarity scale has been utilized as a predictor of additional actions such as support for tourism development ([Woosnam et al., 2009](#); [Woosnam & Norman, 2010](#)), the impact of festivals and support for festival development ([Zou et al., 2021](#)), the effect on tourist satisfaction and destination loyalty ([M. Zhou & Yu, 2022](#)), and social cohesion. Distance and emotional solidarity have been studied increasingly as potential indicators of public support for tourism expansion ([Phuc & Nguyen, 2023](#)). Residents' opinions on tourism's effects (as judged by the tourism impact attitude scale) can be predicted, for instance, by their level of natural friendliness, sympathy, and emotional connection, as demonstrated initially ([Woosnam & Norman, 2010](#)).

This was then followed by research by Woosnam, who found a similar correlation between people's attitudes and support for tourism and their level of emotional solidarity in a rural setting in Malaysia ([Woosnam et al., 2009](#)). The present evidence from another Asian location, Macau, indicates that citizens' positive evaluations of the impact of festivals and support for such events are significantly explained by a sense of emotional solidarity ([Hasani et al., 2016](#)). Friendly demeanor and sympathetic understanding were more robust indicators than emotional intimacy ([Lai & Hitchcock, 2017](#)), who identified three elements of emotional solidarity explaining different aspects of the perceived impact of tourism in Macau. Meanwhile, the author's study highlights how emotional solidarity promotes destination loyalty via historical tourism, both directly and indirectly. So, here is the study's working theory: H4: Emotional Solidarity Has a Positive Influence on Heritage Tourism.

Cultural heritage tourism is a type of travel in which visitors learn about and engage with a destination's rich history and customs through direct interaction with tangible cultural artifacts. Tourists who have a good time visiting cultural heritage places are more inclined to return to that area in the future, which is why the concept of heritage tourism is important—enjoying the destination's cultural offerings, both those that can be held in one's hands and

those that cannot. In 2021, UNESCO recognized cultural heritage tourism as a distinct subset of travel that "focuses on the historical, natural, and cultural value of a destination ([Ismail et al., 2014](#)).

This concerns "the motivation to experience things, representing past and present periods, at a tourist destination" ([C. K. Lee et al., 2023](#)). The factors that make cultural heritage tourist experiences stand out are the subject of an ever-expanding body of study ([Rao et al., 2022](#)). Booming cultural heritage tourism draws on the area's rich history to enrich the trip for visitors. Professionals in the tourism industry frequently use these tactics. They can take many forms, such as the recreation of historical events or scenarios ([Zhang et al., 2023](#)) or the use of genuine symbolic linkages to the past ([Durlević et al., 2023](#)).

Cultural heritage tourism, by definition, is preoccupied with the past ([Scarpi & Raggiotto, 2023](#)), and as a result, necessitates a separation of time between the historical events that are the focus of the tourism and the present day of the tourist ([Surya & Suwarno, 2023](#)). Heritage tourism, in other words, separates visitors from a destination by inserting a layer of time between them and the experience. Thus, we want to examine cultural heritage tourism through the theoretical lens of construal-level theory ([Durlević et al., 2023](#)). No, we are not the first to apply the cultural heritage theory framework. Tourism-related messages, such as reviews and advertising ([Rao et al., 2022](#)), have been studied in the context of this theory before ([Qiu et al., 2022](#)). Heritage tourism is a medium through which the effects of tourism on visitor loyalty are discussed. These effects concern the iconicity of visitor attractions, existential authenticity, place attachment, and emotional solidarity. Advantages (participation and genuineness) of visiting historic sites. This study's hypothesis, then, is H5: Iconic Tourism has a positive influence on Emotional Solidarity, H6: Existential Authenticity has a positive impact on Emotional Solidarity, H7: Place Attachment has a positive effect on Emotional Solidarity, H8: Emotional Solidarity has a positive impact on Destination Loyalty, H9: Culture Tourism Has a Positive Influence on Destination Loyalty.

2. METHODS

This research approach method is quantitative with a descriptive associative research type that explains the relationship between the variables. Anything the researcher decides to study to gather information about and draw conclusions is considered a research variable. Fixed, dependent, and moderating variables were utilized in this study ([Suwarno & Nugroho, 2023](#)). Indonesian have 1,836 tourist villages spread across eight islands, and they are still in the pioneering, developing, and advanced categories; therefore, by 2024, 244 tourist villages will occupy the position of independent tourist village; therefore, the tourist village must have high tourist visit to move to the separate category. Heritage tourism, which encompasses the Iconicity of Visitor Attractions, Existential Authenticity, place attachment, and emotional solidarity towards destination loyalty, is required in tourist communities to promote tourist visits.

Those between the ages of 25 and 50 who frequently visited tourist places or whose interests included travel, especially those who valued adventure, made up the samples for this study. Sample sizes should be at least five times the number of variable indicators utilized in the study ([Hair et al., 2021](#)). Given that the study's 25 indicators are intended to represent all variables, a sample size of 125 is necessary. However, the number of responders was capped at 155 to account for outliers. This study used a non-probability sampling strategy called purposive sampling. The information was gathered using a Google Forms online survey. From

June 2023 to September 2023, a survey was undertaken in four Toba Samosir tourism communities classified as pioneering and developing.

This study employs the Partial Least Square–Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) to evaluate the research model. PLS-SEM is used to explain the relationship between several variables simultaneously. PLS-SEM consists of two models: the measurement model, which represents how the measured variables represent the construct, and the structural model, which shows how the constructs are. PLS-SEM does not require goodness-of-fit standards (Hair et al., 2021). PLS-SEM tests the model based on the structural model's ability to predict endogenous constructs.

This study's questionnaire has many components. First, respondents' age, location, employment status, and monthly income are asked. You will answer qualifying questions in the second section to ensure sample representation. The next question of the poll asks about the study's indicators. On the 5-point Likert scale used to evaluate each study tool, 1 (strong disagreement), 2 (disagreement), 3 (neutrality), 4 (agreement), and 5 (strong agreement). This study will examine five factors. You can control iconic tourist destinations, personal authenticity, emotional connection to a place, and group cohesion—heritage tourism moderates. The concept of destination loyalty is reliant. The research variables and operationalization are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Variables Operationalization

Variables	Items	Source
Iconicity Of Visitor Attractions	I am amazed by the unique attractions. I like Attraction flagships. I like Attraction Iconicity. I will convey it through WOM attraction.	(Xu et al., 2020)
Existential Authenticity	I am very amazed Objective Authenticity I am very amazed by Constructive Authenticity. I am amazed that Perceived Cultural. I am amazed that Authentic living.	(Belhassen et al., 2008 ; Buchmann et al., 2010 ; H. Kim & Jamal, 2007 ; Pons, 2003 ; Steiner & Reisinger, 2006)
Place Attachment	I like Place Dependence I like Affective Attachment. I like the Cognition Attachment I like Behavior Attachment	(Bricker & Kerstetter, 2000 ; Kyle et al., 2005 ; J. Lee et al., 2012)
Emotional Solidarity	I like Shared Beliefs I like Share Behavior I like Interaction I like Emotional closeness.	(Ribeiro et al., 2018)
Heritage Tourism	I like local festivals. I like Traditional Custom I like Learning local skills.	(X. Wang & Leou, 2015)

Variables	Items	Source
	I like Special Souvenir	
Destination Loyalty	I will recommend the tourist village to friends I will recommend the tourism village to my family. Recommending the tourist village will inspire others. Another tourist will hear good things from me. I would return to this tourist village.	(Vidon et al., 2018)

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Results

Table 2. Demographic Respondent

	Respondent Factors	N = 155	%
Genders	Male	59	38 %
	Femal	96	62 %
Age (years)	e 20-29	47	30 %
	30-39	50	32 %
	40-49	31	20 %
	Up 49	27	18 %
Domicile	Up 49	105	68 %
	Medan	50	32 %
Occupation	Outside	54	35 %
	Medan	39	25 %
	Employee private sector	23	15 %
	Employee public sector	20	13 %
Income (IDR)	Self-employed	19	12 %
	Student	8	5 %
	Housewives	54	35 %
	3.5 - 5.5 Bio	70	45 %
	5.6 - 7.5 Bio	23	15 %
	7.6 – 10 Bio		
	> 11 Bio		

Research data was acquired via social media questionnaires. We collected 155 respondents. Table 2 shows the respondent profile. Table 2 reveals that 62% of responders are 30-39-year-old women. About 68% of respondents live in Medan. Up to 35% of respondents work privately. 45% of respondents earn 7,6-10 Bio IDR.

The measurement model is assessed through confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) that tests convergent and discriminant validity. The concurrent validity of the constructs is established through composite reliability (CR) and average variance extracted (AVE) values. Indicators of a variable can be declared valid if it has an AVE value and factor loading value

of more than 0.5 ([Hair et al., 2021](#)). In addition, a variable can be declared reliable if it has Cronbach's Alpha value above 0.6 and a CR value above 0.7 ([Malhotra, 2015](#)). The result of validity testing is as follows in Table 3:

Table 3. Convergent Validity Testing Result

Variables	Indicators	Factor Loading	AVE	CA	CR	Conclusion
Iconicity of Visitor Attractions			0,724	0,873	0,913	Reliable
	Unique Attractions	0,827				Valid
	Attraction Flagships	0,892				Valid
	Attraction Iconicity	0,872				Valid
	Word of Mouth Attraction	0,863				Valid
Existential Authenticity			0,741	0,882	0,919	Reliable
	Objective Authenticity	0,850				Valid
	Constructive Authenticity	0,906				Valid
	Perceived Cultural	0,903				Valid
	Authentic Living	0,779				Valid
Place Attachment			0,824	0,929	0,949	Reliable
	Place Dependence	0,926				Valid
	Affective Attachment	0,937				Valid
	Cognition Attachment	0,935				Valid
	Behavior Attachment	0,829				Valid
Emotional Solidarity			0,784	0,907	0,935	Reliable
	Shared Beliefs	0,914				Valid
	Share Behavior	0,909				Valid
	Interaction	0,817				Valid
	Emotional closeness	0,899				Valid
Heritage Tourism			0,715	0,867	0,909	Reliable
	Local festivals	0,836				Valid
	Traditional Custom	0,859				Valid
	Learning local skills	0,887				Valid
	Special Souvenir	0,802				Valid
Destination Loyalty			0,784	0,930	0,947	Reliable
	Recommend to Friend	0,917				Valid
	Recommend Family members	0,896				Valid
	Encourage other people	0,900				Valid
	Spread positive WOM	0,918				Valid
	Repeat Visits	0,789				Valid

The result shows in Table 3 that all the research indicators are valid because they have an AVE value and factor loading value of more than 0.5. All the research indicators are also reliable because they have Cronbach's Alpha value above 0.6 and a CR value above 0.7 ([Hair](#)

et al., 2021)

Table 4. Discriminant Validity Testing Result

Variable	DL	ES	EA	HT	IVA	PA
Destination Loyalty (DL)	0,885					
Emotional Solidarity (ES)	0,794	0,885				
Existential Authenticity (EA)	0,730	0,803	0,861			
Heritage Tourism (HT)	0,817	0,797	0,680	0,846		
Iconicity of Visitor Attractions (IVA)	0,748	0,873	0,799	0,698	0,851	
Place Attachment (PA)	0,578	0,789	0,800	0,685	0,659	0,908

Discriminant validity (Table 4) ensures that each indicator of the latent variable is not the same as other latent variables (Hair et al., 2021). The discriminant validity of a model can be concluded as good if an indicator of the latent variable has a loading value more significant than the loading value of the indicators on other latent variables. Discriminant validity can be done by looking at the test results of the Fornell-Larcker criteria. The results of the Fornell-Larcker criteria test above show that each variable has the highest value compared to others.

Structural model testing was carried out to evaluate the level of accuracy of the research model formed by several variables and indicators. Measuring the accuracy of the influence of exogenous variables on endogenous variables in the research model can be seen in the coefficient of determination (R²). In the 0-1 range, if the R² value is 0.720, it can be said that the level of accuracy is strong. If the R² value is 0.5, it can be said to be at a medium level of accuracy, and an R² value of 0.839 has a high level of accuracy.

The following results of testing the coefficient of determination in the structural model: Table 5 shows the R² value of the review benefit variable of 0.839, meaning that the exogenous variable, positive emotional solidarity, contributes 83.9% in influencing destination loyalty. Other variables outside the scope of this research determine the remaining 16.1%. Other variables outside the model affect them. Therefore, the significant contribution of the influence of exogenous variables on destination loyalty in this research has a high level of accuracy.

Table 5. Coefficient of Determination Testing Result

Variables	Coefficient of Determination (R ²)	Conclusion
Destination Loyalty (Y)	0,720	Moderate level of accuracy
Emotional Solidarity (X4)	0,839	High level of accuracy
Heritage Tourism (Z)	0,635	Moderate level of accuracy

The heritage tourism variable has an R² value of 0.635, meaning that exogenous variables such as positive heritage tourism and emotional solidarity contribute 63.5% in influencing destination loyalty. Other variables outside the scope of this research influence the remaining 36.5%. Therefore, the influence of the contribution of exogenous variables on destination loyalty in this research can be categorized as a medium level of accuracy. The destination loyalty variable has an R² value of 0.720, meaning that the exogenous variable in this study contributes 72.0% to influencing heritage tourism. Other variables outside the scope of the research influence the remaining 20.8%. Therefore, the contribution of exogenous variables to brand attitude in this research has a moderate level of accuracy.

Figure 1. SEM Model Results (standardized coefficients shown)

Hypotheses testing can be seen from the value of the path coefficient, t-value, and p-values. The hypothesis can be accepted if it has a path coefficient value close to t-value >1.645 and a p-value <0.05. Based on the hypothesis testing result, from six hypotheses in this study, eight ideas were accepted, and one was rejected. According to hypothesis testing in Table 6, the iconic visitor attraction to heritage tourism is positive and insignificant since the path coefficient is 0.007 and the p-value is 0.961. Existential authenticity positively and insignificantly affects heritage tourism with a path coefficient of 0.050 and a p-value of 0.634. Other than that, place attachment has a positive and negligible effect on heritage tourism, with a path coefficient of 0.129 and a p-value of 0.317.

Hypothesis testing shows that emotional solidarity positively affects historical tourism with a path coefficient of 0.649 and a p-value of 0.000. With a path coefficient of 0.618 and a p-value of 0.000, visitor attractions positively and significantly affect emotional solidarity. Emotional solidarity influences existential authenticity and has a positive and negligible path coefficient of 0.012 and a p-value of 0.888.

Hypothesis testing shows that Place attachment positively affects emotional solidarity with a path coefficient of 0.372 and a p-value of 0.000. He also proved that H7 was accepted because its path coefficient was 0.504 and the p-value was 0.002. The mediation test shows heritage tourism positively and significantly affects destination loyalty through other variables like iconic visitor of attraction, existential authenticity, place attachment, and emotional solidarity with a path coefficient of 0.392 and a p-value of 0.000.

Table 6. Hypotheses Testing Result

Hypotheses	Path	Coefficient	T-Value	P-Value	Conclusion
H1	IVA → HT	0,007	0,049	0,961	Rejected
H2	EA → HT	0,050	0,477	0,634	Rejected
H3	PA → HT	0,129	1,001	0,317	Rejected
H4	ES → HT	0,649	4,196	0,000	Accepted
H5	IVA → ES	0,618	9,803	0,000	Accepted
H6	EA → ES	0,012	0,140	0,888	Rejected
H7	PA → ES	0,372	4,550	0,000	Accepted
H8	ES → DL	0,504	3,099	0,002	Accepted
H9	HT → DL	0,392	5,145	0,000	Accepted

Note: Iconicity of Visitor Attractions (IVA), Heritage Tourism (HT), Existential Authenticity (EA), Place Attachment (PA), Emotional Solidarity (ES), Destination Loyalty (DL)

Discussion

This research confirms the relationship between heritage tourism and destination loyalty in the context of tourists visiting tourist villages. The effect states that heritage tourism mediates the iconic visitor relationship of attraction, existential authenticity, place attachment, and emotional solidarity toward destination loyalty. Today's tourism will continue to target customers in the digital era. Traditional marketing approaches divide customers into specific groups (Suwarno, 2024). The results of hypothesis testing show that the iconic visitor attraction is positive but insignificant for heritage tourism, which is positive and essential. Multiple prior studies are consistent with these findings. The impacts of perceptions of flagships and iconicity on word of mouth for attractions and destinations are supported by this hypothesis. Authenticating ethnic tourism attractions is a signal that positively influences destination loyalty (Xu et al., 2020). Historical tourism is persuasive and can shape visitors' feelings about their time in a location (Yuan et al., 2019).

The results of hypothesis testing show that cultural heritage tourism has a positive and significant effect on place attachment. A positive and significant favorable influence on visitors' heritage, experiences, attachment to heritage sites, and sustainable heritage (Yuan et al., 2019). Thus, cultural heritage site managers need help balancing consumption and conservation. This requires the promotion of more sustainable behavior among cultural heritage consumers. Heritage tourism is among the most critical factors influencing destination loyalty (Alrawadieh et al., 2019). That is why self-identification with heritage tourism sites, visitor involvement, and destination loyalty: heritage tourism's overall perceived mediating effect can influence destination loyalty. The place attachment directly affects loyalty, and the two dimensions of emotional solidarity and, in turn, emotional solidarity have a positive effect on loyalty (Hsu & Scott, 2020; Patwardhan et al., 2020; Prayag & Lee, 2019; Tsaor et al., 2019). Additionally, it was found that emotional solidarity partially mediates the effect of place attachment on destination loyalty.

The results of hypothesis testing show that emotional solidarity has a positive and significant effect on destination loyalty. This supports the findings which state that the concept of emotional solidarity originates from early times classical sociological work (Joo et al., 2020) and has taken many forms over the years (Patwardhan et al., 2020), from affective, functional, mechanical, and organic, friends, groups, intergenerational, and most recently tourism (Hsu & Scott, 2020). It can also be seen that heritage tourism has a positive and significant effect on destination loyalty. This is by research to empirically explore existential

authenticity from the visitor's perspective (Fu, 2020). Bearing that existentialism invites people to examine the authenticity of their personal and community lives, various efforts have been made, including inherited traditional customs that require holders of conventional culture to give them life (Yi et al., 2017).

In the process of providing heritage, simple and classic techniques used by local communities in making tools, cooking, and so on are part of the intangible heritage of a site. Souvenirs themselves are part of the authentic experience (Yi et al., 2017, 2018), and authentic experiences are gained through eating traditionally prepared food way (Crozier, 2010; Kong et al., 2022; Lu et al., 2022; Paras et al., 2022; Purwanto & Harani, 2020), and through local people's experiences of lifestyle (Carson & Carson, 2018; Dias et al., 2023; Morón-Corujeira & Fusté-Forné, 2022). Only if they follow a traditional way of life can residents (who preserve local traditional culture) make authentic food, products, or souvenirs and give away original cultural performances. Investigating tourists' motivations for purchasing souvenirs (Brown, 2013) identified the importance of souvenirs as reminders to the tourists who bought them based on their experiences (although souvenirs are also given as gifts).

4. CONCLUSION

This study examines how iconic tourist appeal, existential authenticity, place attachment, and emotional solidarity affect destination loyalty through historical tourism. The findings show that iconic visitor of attraction, existential authenticity, place attachment, and emotional solidarity all have positive but not significant effects on heritage tourism. The research found that iconicity of visitor attractions has a positive and significant effect on emotional solidarity, existential authenticity has a positive but not significant effect, and place attachment has a positive and significant effect.

Other findings show that emotional solidarity and heritage tourism as mediating variables positively and significantly affect destination loyalty. Existential authenticity concerns travelers, while authenticity concerns objects, culture, etc. Existentialists want authenticity in personal life and modern society, especially rural groups. Tourism travelers seek identity and a tourism environment and its aspects. To develop a tourist village from a pioneering one to a developed one, one must explore the iconic visitor attraction, existential authenticity, place attachment, and emotional solidarity of tourists. The above factors will increase tourists' interest in visiting the tourist village. Increasing tourist visits will improve tourist village classifications and encourage autonomous villages. Unique, flagship, iconicity, and word-of-mouth attractions must be considered.

In addition, legacy tourism must emphasize traditional customs, local festivals, learning local skills, and distinctive products to change tourist villages. Existential authenticity prioritizes objective authenticity, constructive authenticity, perceived culture, and authentic life. Place attachment, place dependence, affective attachment, cognitive attachment, and behavioral attachment must be considered by tourism policymakers, particularly local governments and hotel and restaurant operators in tourist village destinations.

This study has significant drawbacks. First, this study only investigates historical tourism in pilot and growing tourist communities, not in advanced and independent cities. Future research can read. Thus, this research must be continued in developed and independent tourist communities by adding variables like perceived value, digital promotion, and sustainable tourism. Second, this study only sampled Millennial women, but senior travelers

may be studied.

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